

IN VITRO STUDIES ON THE GROWTH AND ZN CONTENT BY SEED PRIMING METHOD OF BIOINSPIRED ZINC OXIDE NANOPARTICLES IN WHEAT (*Triticum aestivum* L.)

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Abstract

Zinc (Zn) deficiency remains a serious health concern for both humans and crops, particularly in underdeveloped nations where insufficient food consumption is the primary cause. The primary cause of this is the widespread eating of high quantities of grains lacking in zinc across the globe. The practise of "biofortifying" grains with zinc can help to overcome this issue. Nanotechnology is one approach for increasing crop nutritional value since some designed nanoparticles (NPs) may be used as fertiliser. Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) can be employed in biofortification of wheat. The current study prepared ZnO NPs using the green synthesis method, characterised them using UV-visible spectrophotometry and particle size analysis techniques and then evaluated the effect of ZnO NPs by seed priming (25, 50, 75, 100, 300, 500 ppm) on growth and Zn uptake in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). UV-visible spectrophotometry revealed an absorbance peak at 362 nm and 365 nm for the zinc oxide nanoparticles synthesized from wheat root extract and endophytic bacteria, respectively also, the average size of zinc oxide nanoparticles synthesized from wheat root extract was 19.66 nm and from endophytic bacteria was 37.3 nm according to particle size analysis. Seed priming of ZnO NP significantly improved wheat biomass, photosynthesis, growth parameters and Zn content. ZnO NPs were shown to have a notably greater concentration of zinc in the straw and grains of wheat compared to the control, indicating that these particles might be employed as a source of zinc with the goal of reducing zinc shortage in plants. Nonetheless, doing field research with varying conditions and plant species might augment the mechanistic comprehension of NPs' suitability in this field.

Keywords: Zinc oxide (ZnO), nano particles (NPs), wheat root extract, endophytic bacterium, seed priming, Zn biofortification.

Introduction

Zn deficiency is a major global health concern and a barrier to meeting agricultural production objectives as zinc is regarded as an essential element (Cakmak *et al.*, 2018; Gregory *et al.*, 2017 and Shivay *et al.*, 2008). A significant percentage of food is produced using cereal-based products, which have a low zinc content and cannot provide enough zinc for human consumption. (Grusak *et al.*, 2005). Small amounts of zinc, such as those found in cereal grains like wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) may not be sufficient for human consumption. The development and production of crops were also adversely impacted by zinc deficiency and the toxicity of other heavy metals (Cakmak *et al.*, 2009 and Rizwan *et al.*, 2017).

Zn deficiency in plants might be alleviated by a variety of strategies, including crop biofortification, dietary diversity, supplementation and cereals (Gregory *et al.*, 2017). Currently, a variety of objectives and circumstances are being met by the application of nanotechnology in agriculture (Awad *et al.*, 2019). Another usage for nanoparticles (NPs) is as a source of vital nutrients for plants (Rizwan *et al.*, 2017). In terms of seed growth, transpiration rate, germination rate and plant biomass, nanoparticles are less effective. On the other hand, during the initial phases of wheat plant development, these nanoparticles lengthen the roots (Larue *et al.*, 2012).

Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles are the most often utilised NPs in the world and there have been reports of both good and negative impacts they may have on the ecosystem. For wheat plants, ZnO nanoparticles are applied using a variety of techniques, including soil mixing, foliar spray and seed priming (Rizwan *et al.*, 2017). Seed priming is an easy and affordable way to increase the germination rate of seeds by allowing them to quickly absorb and revitalise their metabolism. This reduces inherent physiological non-uniformity in germination. Crop productivity and growth quality can both be enhanced by the seed priming technique. To assess the impact of ZnO NPs on wheat growth parameters and plant absorption of zinc, the seed priming approach was chosen in order to remove soil constraints (Rico *et al.*, 2014).

Plant material and Endophytic Bacterium

The present study used plant material i.e. Wheat variety PDKV Sardar (AKAW 4210-6), which was obtained from the Wheat Research Unit,

Dr. PDKV, Akola. Additionally, bacterial endophyte culture was isolated from wheat root for use in the nanoparticle synthesis.

Chemicals used during the investigation

Numerous chemicals were acquired from Himedia and SRL for the synthesis and characterization studies of nanoparticles as specified in the particular procedure.

Preparation of wheat root extract

The 5 g of fresh roots of the chosen plant material were weighed and to get rid of the dust, they were first cleaned with tap water and then distilled water. After chopping the roots into tiny bits, 500 ml of deionized water were used to grind them using a mortar and pestle until a fine paste was created. The homogeneous mixture was brought to a boil for 30 minutes at 60-70°C. Filter paper was used to filter the slurry once it had cooled. To extract only the supernatant, the filtrate was centrifuged for 30 minutes at 10,000 rpm in order to exclude the heavy biomass. Whatman filter paper No. 1 was used once again to filter the supernatant aqueous solution, which was then refrigerated for further examination.

Green synthesis of nanoparticles (ZnO-NPs) from wheat root

Green synthesis was used to synthesis the nanoparticles, following some changes to Bagheri *et al.*, (2019) methodology. Sterile double-distilled water was used to make a 15 mM solution of zinc acetate, a salt. Using a magnetic stirrer, 100 ml of 15 mM metal ion solutions were combined with 0.5% root extract at 90 °C for 45 minutes in an Erlenmeyer flask. It was added to a 3% 1N NaOH solution after 45 minutes. The precipitate was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 6-8 minutes after adding a 3% 1 N NaOH solution. To ensure their purity, they were then cleaned twice with sterile double distilled water. After that, the precipitate was dried in a vacuum concentrator for 45 minutes at 60 °C. The precipitate was dried and then kept in room temperature storage.

Green synthesis of (ZnO-NPs) nanoparticles from endophytic bacterium

Bacterial strain and culture conditions

Using nutritional agar medium, the fresh bacterial strain *P. guariconensis* was cultured for 24 hours at 37 °C. Additionally, after 24 hours at 37 °C and constant orbital shaking at 150 rpm, the culture was

subcultured into nutrient broth medium. For the production of ZnO NPs, the supernatant was obtained from an overnight bacterial culture following centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes.

Synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles

The little modifications were made in the methodology of Neethipathi *et al.*, (2017) where the green synthesis approach was used to synthesize the zinc oxide nanoparticles. 100 ml of the zinc nitrate solution (1 mM) and 100 ml cell-free supernatant were added to 500 ml beaker. The mixed solution-filled beaker was dried at 120 °C after being stirred by a magnetic stirrer for 24 hours at room temperature.

Characterization of Nanoparticles

UV Visible spectrophotometer

It is the primary method for determining the stability, molar absorbance and synthesis of metal nanoparticles. The closely spaced conduction and valence bands are home to free-flowing electrons. These electrons generate SPR (Surface Plasmon Resonance), which results in the production of an absorption band, as a result of their collective oscillation in resonance with light.

Particle size analysis

The size and distribution of the particles in a system are the most important characteristics. It regulates the toxicity, targeting ability, biological destiny and in vivo distribution of nanoparticles.

Additionally, it can have an impact on the nanoparticles surface area and stability. The most popular and speedier methods for estimating particle size these days are dynamic light scattering and photon-correlation spectroscopy. Typically, scanning or transmission electron microscopy (SEM or TEM) is used to validate the results of photon-correlation spectroscopy.

Pot Experiment:

Prior to planting, wheat seedlings were primed with varying ZnO NP concentrations (25, 50, 75, 100, 300, and 500 ppm) while being continuously aerated for about 24 hours. Following this, seeds were saved for later use after being cleaned with distilled water and allowed to air dry in the shade. Using a completely randomised design (CRD) with three replicates of each treatment, primed seeds were sowed in plastic pots with 3.0 kg of soil. After seven days of germination, the initial ten seeds in each pot were trimmed to six seedlings each. Fertiliser was added to each pot at a rate of 120-50-25 kg ha⁻¹ for urea (N), diammonium phosphate (DAP) and potassium sulphate, respectively. DAP and K were applied in whole, while half of the N was applied at the time of sowing and the other half was applied 35 days later. Regular random rotation was carried out primarily to reduce the experiment's environmental influences.

Fig. 1 Synthesis of ZnO NPs from wheat root extract

(i) Filtrate of root extract; (ii) 15 mM Zinc Acetate + 0.5 % root extract + boiling at 90°C; (iii) Precipitation after addition of 3 % NaOH; (iv) After centrifugation nanoparticles dried in vacuum concentrator; (v) Nanoparticles in powder form.

Fig. 2 Synthesis of ZnO NPs from endophytic bacterium

(i) Cell free supernatant of endophytic bacterium; (ii) 15 mM Zinc Acetate + 0.5 % cell free supernatant + boiling at 90°C; (iii) Precipitation after addition of 3 % NaOH; (iv) After centrifugation nanoparticles dried in vacuum concentrator; (v) Nanoparticles in powder form.

Fig. 3 UV-visible spectrometry of ZnO NPs synthesized from wheat root extract

Fig. 4 UV-visible spectrometry of ZnO NPs synthesized from endophytic bacterium

Fig. 5 Particle size analysis of ZnO NPs synthesized from wheat root extract

Fig. 6 Particle size analysis of ZnO NPs synthesized from endophytic bacterium

Control

Treatments overview at 30 DAS

Plate. 1 Treatments overview

Results:**Green synthesis of metal nanoparticles**

Following the methodology of Bagheri *et al.*, 2019 and Neethipathi *et al.*, (2017), respectively, with minor modifications, wheat root extract and endophytic bacteria were used to green synthesis of metal nanoparticles.

Synthesis of ZnO NPs from wheat root extract:

Wheat root extract was used to synthesize biogenic zinc oxide nanoparticles using Bagheri *et al.*, 2019 procedure with the little modifications. Zinc oxide nanoparticles were synthesised using 15 mM zinc acetate solution, the metal precursor for the synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles. The addition of wheat root extract and NaOH to the colourless solution resulted in a white precipitation, signifying the synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles, as illustrated in (Fig. 1) Because wheat root extract functions as both a stabilising and reducing agent, zinc oxide nanoparticle synthesis can employ secondary metabolites as a capping agent.

Synthesis of ZnO NPs from endophytic bacterium

Cell-free extract of endophytic bacteria was used to carry out the green synthesis of zinc nanoparticles using a slightly modification of Neethipathi *et al.*, 2017 methodology. The metal precursor for the synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles, zinc acetate solution (15 mM), was used to synthesise the nanoparticles. Zinc acetate solution was colourless before to reaction; but, as shown in (Fig. 2), it became brown after reacting with *P. guariconensis* culture supernatant. This outcome suggests that zinc oxide nanoparticles are being synthesised.

Characterization of synthesized ZnO NPs**UV Visible spectrophotometer analysis:**

Using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer, the synthesis of ZnO-NPs from wheat root extract and endophytic bacteria was verified. ZnO-NPs synthesised from endophytic bacteria and wheat root extract, respectively, showed an absorbance peak at 362 nm and 365 nm. ZnO NPs synthesised from wheat root extract had an absorbance of 1.6 on

the spectrophotometer. As seen in (Fig. 3), a typical pick is observed. Bagheri *et al.*, (2019) reported similar outcomes. After synthesis zinc oxide nanoparticles from *S. bailalensis* root extract, the absorbance peak of the UV-visible spectrophotometer, which spans from 250 to 550 nm, signifies the synthesis of the nanoparticles. ZnO NPs synthesised from endophytic bacteria had an absorbance of 0.8 on the spectrophotometer. As seen in (Fig. 4), a typical pick is observed. Neethipathi *et al.* (2017) reported similar outcomes. The absorbance peak of the UV-visible spectrophotometer spans from 300 to 900 nm, and they synthesized the zinc oxide nanoparticles from the cell-free supernatant of endophytic bacteria.

Particle size analysis:

The Nanoparticles Tracking Analysis (NTA) method was used to determine the particle size distribution. As demonstrated in (Figs. 5) & (Fig. 6), the average size of zinc oxide nanoparticles synthesised from endophytic bacteria was 37.3 nm and the particle size distribution curve and particle intensity/size revealed that these values were acquired from wheat root extract at 19.66 nm. In accordance with the nanoparticle definition, it was discovered that the ZnO nanoparticles synthesised from endophytic bacteria and wheat root extract were smaller than 100 nm. Zinc oxide nanostructured particles were synthesised using chemical and biological techniques, according to Sangeetha (2011). Zinc nitrate and Aloe vera leaf extract were used to synthesis well-rounded, very stable zinc oxide nanoparticles. A typical size of 25-40 nm was discovered. An effective reducing agent, *Rubus fairholmianus* root extract (RE), was used by Rajendran *et al.*, (2021) to synthesis ZnO NPs. Using the Debye-Scherrer equation, an average particle size of 11.34 nm was obtained. RE-ZnO NPs were found to be spherical in form and to have clusters (1-100 nm) by SEM examination.

Effect of seed treatments of ZnO NPs synthesized from WRE and ENB on yield, its attributes and zinc content of wheat in pot culture under greenhouse conditions.

Plant growth and biomass

Plant height was significantly affected by different treatments ranging from 63.84 cm to 69.96 cm (**Fig. 10(a)**). Treatment of 100 ppm (T_5) nanoparticles synthesized from wheat root extract recorded highest plant height (69.96 cm). However, this treatment was found to be statistically at par with all the treatments as given in **Table 1**.

Spike length was significantly affected by different treatments ranging from 10.3 cm to 12.7 cm (**Fig. 10(a)**). Treatment of 100 ppm (T_5) nanoparticles synthesized from wheat root extract recorded highest spike length (12.7 cm). However, this treatment was found to be statistically at par with all the treatments as reported in **Table 1**.

Dry weight of root was significantly affected by different treatments ranging from 6.24 g to 9.83 g (**Fig. 10(a)**). Treatment of 100 ppm (T_5) nanoparticles synthesized from wheat root extract showed the highest dry weight of root (9.83 g). However, this treatment was found to be statistically at par with all the treatments except T_2 , T_3 , T_8 , T_9 and T_{10} as given in **Table 1**.

Dry weight of shoot was significantly affected by different treatments ranging from 10.81 g to 18.17 g (**Fig. 10(a)**). Treatment of 100 ppm (T_5) nanoparticles synthesized from wheat root extract produced highest dry weight of shoot (18.17 g). However, this treatment was found to be statistically at par with all the treatments except T_2 , T_3 , T_8 and T_9 as reported in **Table 1**.

Grain yield per plant was significantly affected by different treatments ranging from 7.81 g to 8.90 g (**Fig. 10(a)**). Treatment of 100 ppm (T_5) nanoparticles synthesized from wheat root extract showed highest grain yield per plant (8.90 g). However, this treatment was found to be statistically at par with all the treatments as depicted in **Table 1**.

Straw yield per plant was significantly affected by different treatments ranging from 9.36 g to 10.47 g (**Fig. 10(a)**). Treatment of 100 ppm (T_5) nanoparticles synthesized from wheat root extract produced highest straw yield per plant (10.47 g). However, this treatment was found to be statistically at par with all other treatments as given in **Table 1**.

Fig. 10(a). Effect of seed treatments of ZnO NPs synthesized from WRE and ENB on plant height, spike length, dry weight of root, dry weight of shoot, grain yield per plant and straw yield per plant in pot culture under greenhouse conditions.

Photosynthetic attributes

Chlorophyll content at 30 days was significantly affected by different treatments ranging from 3.22 mg g^{-1} to 3.75 mg g^{-1} (**Fig. 10(b)**). Treatment of 100 ppm (T_5) nanoparticles synthesized from wheat root extract recorded highest chlorophyll content at 30 days (3.75 mg g^{-1}). However, this treatment was found to be statistically at par with all other treatments as given **Table 1**.

Chlorophyll content at 60 days was significantly affected by different treatments ranging from 1.89 mg g^{-1} to 2.67 mg g^{-1} (**Fig. 10(b)**). Treatment of 100 ppm (T_5) nanoparticles synthesized from wheat root extract depicted highest chlorophyll content at 60 days (2.67 mg g^{-1}). However, this treatment was found to be statistically at par with all the treatments as depicted in **Table 1**.

Fig. 10(b). Effect of seed treatments of ZnO NPs synthesized from WRE and ENB on chlorophyll content at 30 days and chlorophyll content at 60 days in pot culture under greenhouse conditions.

Zinc content in plants

Zinc content in grain was significantly affected by different treatments ranging from 39.10 mg kg^{-1} to 43.88 mg kg^{-1} (Fig. 10(c)). Treatment of 100 ppm (T_5) nanoparticles synthesized from wheat root extract recorded highest zinc content in grain (43.88 mg kg^{-1}). However, this treatment was found to be statistically at par with all the treatments as depicted in Table 1.

Zinc content in straw was significantly affected by different treatments ranging from 41.21 mg kg^{-1} to 46.38 mg kg^{-1} (Fig. 10(c)). Treatment of 100 ppm (T_5) nanoparticles synthesized from wheat root extract procreated highest zinc content in straw (46.38 mg kg^{-1}). However, this treatment was found to be statistically at par with all the treatments as given in Table 1.

Fig. 10(c). Effect of seed treatments of ZnO NPs synthesized from WRE and ENB on Zn content in grain and Zn content in straw in pot culture under greenhouse conditions.

Discussion:

The green synthesis method has been selected for the synthesis of ZnO NPs due to its unique feature of eco-friendliness compared to physical vapor deposition (PVD) and chemical vapor deposition (CVD). UV-visible spectroscopy confirms that ZnO NPs were synthesized from wheat root extract and endophytic bacterium by measuring the absorbance peak at 362 nm and 365 nm, respectively. ZnO NPs synthesized from wheat root extract had an absorbance of 1.6 on the spectrophotometer. As seen in (Fig. 3), a typical pick is observed. ZnO NPs synthesized from endophytic bacterium had an absorbance of 0.8 on the spectrophotometer. As seen in (Fig. 4), a typical pick is observed. The particle size distribution curve and particle intensity/size showed that the average size of Zinc oxide nanoparticles from wheat root extract was 19.66 nm and Zinc oxide nanoparticles from endophytic bacteria was 37.3 nm as shown in (Fig. 5) & (Fig. 6)

According to our findings, ZnO NPs enhanced plant growth and photosynthesis in comparison to the control (Fig. 10(a)). The present findings unequivocally show that ZnO NPs work to improve plant production and growth. One potential strategy to improve plant development with Zn availability is seed priming. The mobilization of nutrients like phosphate from the soil and the proliferation of

microorganisms, particularly in the rhizosphere, may be the cause of the increased plant growth when NPs are used (Raliya *et al.*, 2013).

Seed priming with ZnO NPs increased the Zn concentrations in grain and straw than control (Plate 1). According to Rizwan *et al.* (2017), the effects of Zn uptake from NPs depend on the dosages and experimental setup. Zn concentrations in cucumber plant shoots were found to be lower when Zn NPs (125 mg kg^{-1}) were used than when Zn concentrations of 25 mg kg^{-1} . This difference in Zn concentration may have resulted from root deformation at higher Zn levels (Moghaddasi *et al.*, 2013). However, it was noted that NPs may have penetrated plant cells more deeply in plants treated with NPs, as evidenced by the increase in zinc contents in those plants (Moghaddasi *et al.*, 2017). Our findings thus suggested that seed priming could be a useful strategy for raising plant grain Zn contents. Overall, our findings can assist the fertilizer industry in making decisions on the synthesis of nanofertilizers, particularly ZnO NPs for plant nutrition, which will ultimately aid in lowering plant and human zinc deficiencies.

Conclusions:

Finally, wheat root extract and endophytic bacteria can be used as a reducing agent to synthesize ZnO NPs. ZnO NP synthesis was shown by UV-visible spectroscopy and particle size analysis. Seed priming

(25, 50, 75, 100, 300, 500 ppm) of ZnO NPs resulted in a linear increase in plant growth, photosynthesis, biomass and Zn content in grain and straw compared to the control. Therefore, ZnO NPs might be utilised as a Zn supply to lessen wheat Zn deficiency. Field investigations with varying nanostructure sizes, shapes, circumstances and plants, however, could improve our understanding of the mechanisms behind the practicality of NPs in this field.

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Table 1. Effect of seed treatments of ZnO NPs synthesized from WRE and ENB on yield, its attributes and zinc content in pot culture under greenhouse conditions.

Treatments	Plant height (cm)	Spike length (cm)	Dry weight of root (g)	Dry weight of Shoot (g)	Chloro phyll content at 30 days (mg g ⁻¹)	Chloro phyll content at 60 days (mg g ⁻¹)	Grain yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	Straw yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	Zinc content in grain (mg kg ⁻¹)	Zinc content in straw (mg kg ⁻¹)
T ₁ (Control)	63.84	10.36	6.24	10.81	3.22	1.89	7.81	9.36	39.10	41.21
T ₂ ZnO NPs – WRE (25 ppm)	65.20	10.87	6.82	12.31	3.48	2.32	8.32	10.20	40.00	42.26
T ₃ ZnO NPs – WRE (50 ppm)	66.97	11.28	7.17	13.95	3.54	2.40	8.39	10.28	41.30	43.41
T ₄ ZnO NPs – WRE (75 ppm)	68.06	12.17	8.42	15.02	3.63	2.59	8.57	10.38	43.52	45.70
T ₅ ZnO NPs – WRE (100 ppm)	69.96	12.78	9.83	18.17	3.75	2.67	8.90	10.47	43.88	46.38
T ₆ ZnO NPs – WRE (300 ppm)	69.87	12.69	9.78	18.09	3.74	2.66	8.89	10.46	43.79	46.35
T ₇ ZnO NPs – WRE (500 ppm)	69.68	12.47	9.45	17.96	3.71	2.64	8.87	10.42	43.77	46.34
T ₈ ZnO NPs – ENB (25 ppm)	64.87	10.76	6.68	12.34	3.39	2.27	8.06	10.09	39.79	42.12
T ₉ ZnO NPs – ENB (50 ppm)	66.60	10.95	6.89	13.22	3.51	2.33	8.25	10.22	41.17	43.12
T ₁₀ ZnO NPs – ENB (75 ppm)	67.41	11.77	7.67	14.96	3.57	2.51	8.45	10.31	43.51	45.08
T ₁₁ ZnO NPs – ENB (100 ppm)	69.40	12.57	9.08	16.46	3.68	2.66	8.86	10.43	43.70	45.93
T ₁₂ ZnO NPs – ENB (300 ppm)	69.19	12.47	8.99	16.42	3.66	2.65	8.84	10.42	43.66	45.89
T ₁₃ ZnO NPs – ENB (500 ppm)	69.09	12.29	8.86	16.39	3.64	2.62	8.81	10.40	43.62	45.85
SEM±	1.42	0.52	0.46	0.86	0.10	0.14	0.25	0.20	1.24	1.18
C.D. @ 1 %	5.55	2.03	1.82	3.35	0.40	0.54	0.96	0.77	4.86	4.61

WRE : Wheat root extract, ENB : Endophytic bacteriu